

Supplementary Materials for: Electrostrictive Metamaterial Study: Shaping Fields to Exceed Intrinsic Material Limits

S1 Supplementary Methods

S1.1 Material parameters

Material parameters for PMN–PT–BT used in all simulations are listed in Table S1. The study uses the benchmark simulation parameters from the COMSOL electrostrictive tutorial [1], which approximate experimental values reported by Hom and Shankar [2].

Table S1: Material parameters for PMN–PT–BT, a ternary solid solution of lead magnesium niobate ($\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$, PMN) with 7.7% lead titanate (PbTiO_3 , PT) and 2.5% barium titanate (BaTiO_3 , BT) by volume, at an operating temperature of 5 °C, used in all simulations. Material parameters adopted from the standard COMSOL electrostrictive benchmark [1], which approximates the experimental values reported in [2].

Parameter	Symbol & Unit	Value
Young’s modulus	E (GPa)	105
Poisson’s ratio	ν (–)	0.4
Density	ρ (kg m^{-3})	7900
Electrostriction (longitudinal)	Q_{11} ($\text{m}^4 \text{C}^{-2}$)	0.0133
Electrostriction (transverse)	Q_{12} ($\text{m}^4 \text{C}^{-2}$)	–0.006 06
Saturation polarization	P_s (C m^{-2})	0.2589
Domain wall density parameter	a (MV m^{-1})	0.862 07

S1.2 Full linear-fit statistics for effective electrostriction

Table S2: No-intercept fits on surface-averaged channels (corresponding to main-text Fig. 4). Entries correspond to Q_{11} , Q_{12} , and Q_{44} . Reported are Q^{eff} ($\text{m}^4 \text{C}^{-2}$), R^2 , and 95% confidence intervals.

(a) Q_{11} fits.

Geometry	Q^{eff}	R^2	95% CI
Slab	$1.330\,000 \times 10^{-2}$	1.000 000	$\pm 1.362 \times 10^{-11}$
Design 1	$1.042\,843 \times 10^{-2}$	1.000 000	$\pm 3.868 \times 10^{-8}$
Design 2	$2.288\,095 \times 10^{-2}$	1.000 000	$\pm 3.879 \times 10^{-8}$

(b) Q_{12} fits.

Geometry	Q^{eff}	R^2	95% CI
Slab	$-6.059\,998 \times 10^{-3}$	1.000 000	$\pm 1.981 \times 10^{-11}$
Design 1	$3.749\,780 \times 10^{-3}$	1.000 000	$\pm 1.990 \times 10^{-8}$
Design 2	$3.948\,585 \times 10^{-4}$	1.000 000	$\pm 4.290 \times 10^{-8}$

(c) Q_{44} fits.

Geometry	Q^{eff}	R^2	95% CI
Slab	$1.936\,361 \times 10^{-2}$	0.999 996	$\pm 7.360 \times 10^{-6}$
Design 1	$2.380\,184 \times 10^{-2}$	0.999 991	$\pm 1.990 \times 10^{-5}$
Design 2	$-1.385\,478 \times 10^{-1}$	0.999 955	$\pm 2.696 \times 10^{-4}$

S1.3 Full performance tables referenced by main-text Table 1

Table S3: Energy-aware motion. Surface-averaged displacement magnitude $\langle |u| \rangle_S$, electric energy U_e , elastic energy U_{elastic} , total input energy per cycle $U_{\text{in}} \approx U_e + U_{\text{elastic}}$, and the efficiency proxy $\langle |u| \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}$.

Geometry	U_e (J)	U_{elastic} (J)	U_{in} (J)	$\langle u \rangle_S$ (μm)	$\langle u \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}$ ($\mu\text{m J}^{-1}$)	$(\langle u \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}) / \text{Slab}$
Slab	2.994×10^{-6}	1.799×10^{-9}	2.996×10^{-6}	6.279×10^{-3}	2.096×10^3	1.000
Design-1	1.167×10^{-7}	2.283×10^{-11}	1.168×10^{-7}	3.953×10^{-3}	3.386×10^4	16.154
Design-2	1.591×10^{-7}	4.124×10^{-11}	1.591×10^{-7}	3.747×10^{-3}	2.355×10^4	11.235

Table S4: Actuation per stress. Surface-averaged displacement $\langle |u| \rangle_S$, surface-averaged von Mises stress $\langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$, and the figure of merit $\langle |u| \rangle_S / \langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$.

Geometry	$\langle u \rangle_S$ (μm)	$\langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$ (N m^{-2})	$\langle u \rangle_S / \langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$ ($\mu\text{m m}^2 \text{N}^{-1}$)	$(\langle u \rangle_S / \langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S) / \text{Slab}$
Design-1	3.953×10^{-3}	8.982×10^4	4.401×10^{-8}	1.942
Design-2	3.747×10^{-3}	8.290×10^4	4.520×10^{-8}	1.995
Slab	6.279×10^{-3}	2.771×10^5	2.266×10^{-8}	1.000

Table S5: Directionality metrics at peak phase ($t^* = 0.25$), computed on surface elements and weighted by element area. High-end outliers were trimmed symmetrically by 0.5% of total area before plotting; the $r > 100$ column is reported on the full (untrimmed) data.

Geometry	% area ($r > 1$)	% area ($r > 2$)	% area ($r > 5$)	% area ($r > 100$)
Slab	85.859	58.586	22.727	0.50
Design-1	100.000	99.240	61.434	9.04
Design-2	100.000	98.819	64.495	8.98

S2 Simulation Model Validation

To validate the accuracy of the finite element model (FEM) used in this study for simulating coupled electrostriction in PMN–PT–BT, we verified its implementation against an established numerical benchmark and confirmed consistency with analytical expectations for the material’s constitutive behavior.

S2.1 Constitutive Model Implementation

The simulation employs a constitutive model for the relaxor ferroelectric PMN–PT–BT based on the phenomenological framework developed by Hom and Shankar [2–4]. This model assumes that electrostrictive strain arises quadratically from polarization and incorporates polarization saturation at high electric fields.

Electrostriction contributes additively to the total strain tensor ϵ_{ij} via the electrostrictive strain $\epsilon_{em,ij}$:

$$\epsilon_{em,ij} = Q_{ijkl} P_k P_l, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where P_k and P_l are components of the polarization vector \mathbf{P} , and for isotropic materials, the fourth-order electrostriction tensor Q simplifies to two independent components, Q_{11} and Q_{12} (values listed in Table S1).

Polarization \mathbf{P} is modeled as a nonlinear function of the effective electric field \mathbf{E}_{eff} , using a hyperbolic tangent form to capture saturation:

$$\mathbf{P} = P_s \tanh\left(\frac{|\mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}|}{a}\right) \frac{\mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}}{|\mathbf{E}_{\text{eff}}|}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $P_s = 0.2589 \text{ C m}^{-2}$ is the saturation polarization, and a is a material parameter related to domain wall density. The effective electric field incorporates stress coupling through:

$$E_{\text{eff},l} = E_l + 2\sigma_{ij}Q_{ijkl}P_k, \quad (\text{S3})$$

where stress σ_{ij} is calculated assuming linear elasticity:

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}(\epsilon_{kl} - \epsilon_{em,kl}), \quad (\text{S4})$$

and the total strain ϵ_{kl} is derived from mechanical displacement gradients:

$$\epsilon_{kl} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_l} + \frac{\partial u_l}{\partial x_k} \right). \quad (\text{S5})$$

For isotropic materials, the elasticity tensor C is defined by Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν (Table S1).

The parameter a in Eq. (S2) relates to the material constant k (units m V^{-1}) from the original Hom and Shankar formulation ($|P| = P_s \tanh(k|E|)$) [2] via $a = 1/k$. Using the experimental value $k = 1.16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m V}^{-1}$ at 5°C [3], we obtain:

$$a = \frac{1}{1.16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m V}^{-1}} \approx 0.86207 \text{ MV m}^{-1}. \quad (\text{S6})$$

This value for a aligns with the COMSOL benchmark [1] and is consistently used in all simulations, ensuring consistency between the benchmark and our model implementation.

S2.2 Validation Against COMSOL Benchmark

The primary validation verified the numerical consistency of our finite element implementation against the ‘‘Electrostrictive Disc’’ tutorial model from the COMSOL Application Library [1]. This step confirms that the solver settings, saturation function, and constitutive relations (Sec. S2.1) are correctly defined according to the standard numerical implementation before applying them to the architected geometries.

Due to differing geometries (2D slab with a fixed bottom edge vs. an axisymmetric disc with less mechanical constraint) and boundary conditions, a direct quantitative comparison of absolute field values is less meaningful than verifying the fundamental material response. Figure S1 compares the average P–E and S–E curves from both models.

Figure S1a confirms that both models accurately capture the characteristic non-linear P–E relationship, approaching saturation near $P_s = 0.2589 \text{ C m}^{-2}$. Similarly, Fig. S1b shows qualitative agreement in the S–E response, reflecting the expected symmetric, quadratic-like behavior ($S \propto P^2 \propto E^2$ at low fields) [2]. Quantitative differences at slightly higher fields are reasonably attributed to the distinct mechanical constraints and field distributions inherent to the slab versus disc geometries.

S2.3 Analytical Consistency Checks

Further validation involved quantitative checks against expected physical behavior:

1. **Low-Field Behavior ($S \approx ME^2$):** In the low-field regime, electrostrictive strain (S) should be quadratic with the electric field (E). The effective electrostrictive coefficient $M_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\langle S_{\text{dominant}} \rangle}{\langle E_{\text{dominant}}^2 \rangle}$ was calculated using the lowest non-zero field points:

(a) Dominant Polarization vs. Dominant Electric Field (P–E)

(b) Dominant Strain vs. Dominant Electric Field (S–E)

Figure S1: Comparison of average (a) P–E and (b) S–E responses between the Slab FEM and COMSOL Disc benchmark using identical PMN–PT–BT parameters (Table S1).

- COMSOL Disc: $M_{\text{eff,disc}} \approx 1.18 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2 \text{ V}^{-2}$ (at $E \approx 0.126 \text{ MV m}^{-1}$).
- Slab Model: $M_{\text{eff,slab}} \approx 1.13 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2 \text{ V}^{-2}$ (at $E \approx 0.209 \text{ MV m}^{-1}$).

The agreement within 4% verifies the correct implementation of the low-field quadratic relationship. This magnitude is consistent with experimental data for related materials (e.g., $M_{33} \approx 0.94 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2 \text{ V}^{-2}$ for PMN-10PT [5]).

2. **Saturation Trend:** As seen in Fig. S1a, the simulated P–E curves correctly exhibit saturation towards P_s , consistent with the hyperbolic tangent formulation in Eq. (S2).

The qualitative agreement with the benchmark P–E and S–E characteristics (Fig. S1), quantitative consistency of the low-field M_{eff} , and adherence to expected saturation trends collectively validate the FEM model’s implementation of coupled, non-linear electrostrictive physics for the PMN–PT–BT slab. The solver settings for the FEM model of the architected structures are identical to those established during this validation.

References

- [1] COMSOL Multiphysics. Electrostrictive disc: Modeling nonlinear strain in electrostrictive materials using the mems module. Application library example, COMSOL, 2023.
- [2] Craig L. Hom and Natarajan Shankar. A finite element method for electrostrictive ceramic devices. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 33(12):1757–1779, 1996. doi:10.1016/0020-7683(95)00123-9.
- [3] Craig L. Hom and Natarajan Shankar. A fully coupled constitutive model for electrostrictive ceramic materials. *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, 5(6):795–801, 1994. doi:10.1177/1045389X9400500610.
- [4] Craig L. Hom, Steven M. Pilgrim, Natarajan Shankar, Keith Bridger, Mona Massuda, and Stephen R. Winzer. Calculation of quasi-static electromechanical coupling coefficients for electrostrictive ceramic materials. *IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics and Frequency Control*, 41(4):542–551, 1994. doi:10.1109/58.294116.

- [5] Zeyuan Hou, Ruibin Xiong, Hongjiang Wu, Zujian Wang, Bin Su, Rongbing Su, Xifa Long, and Chao He. Ultralow hysteresis and a giant electrostrictive coefficient in $\text{pb}(\text{mg}_{1/3}\text{nb}_{2/3})\text{o}_3$ -based ferroelectric crystals. *Crystal Growth & Design*, 24(11):4682–4689, 2024. doi:10.1021/acs.cgd.4c00311.